

DEFINING AND MEASURING SOCIAL CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT (CRM) CAPABILITIES

Hyun Gon Kim & Zhan Wang

ABSTRACT

Companies find it necessary to develop new social customer relationship management (CRM) capabilities to facilitate their customer-related performance. This study seeks systematically to conceptualize and measure social CRM capability, defined as a firm's efficiency in integrating and converting social media marketing resources into desired sales revenue and customer relationship outcomes. This definition focuses on the firm's competency in obtaining, generating, organizing, and integrating information from customers' social media engagement to maintain and improve the customer relationship and its own financial performance. Adding to the conventional input–output stochastic frontier model, this study proposes including social media resource inputs and customer-related outcomes to measure social CRM capabilities. An empirical application suggests that social CRM capability is critical; investing in social media technology can lead to substantial CRM benefits and greater market value for the firm. Marketers should focus on developing strategies that emphasize customer relationship building through social media, which allows for more customer involvement and interactions between the customer and the business.

Keywords: Social CRM capabilities, Customer relationship management (CRM), Social media marketing, Stochastic frontier model

INTRODUCTION

The popularity of social media has meant that companies must develop new customer relationship management (CRM) capabilities, beyond traditional format and tactics (Pansari and Kumar 2017; Rapp et al. 2013; Reimann, Schilke, and Thomas 2010; Trainor 2012; Trainor et al. 2011, 2014; Wang and Kim 2017). By integrating social media with existing CRM systems, they can develop new capabilities for enhancing customer satisfaction and effectively leverage these collaborative, interactive platforms to manage their customer relationships (Trainor et al. 2014). In turn, marketing expenses devoted to social media grew by 234% between 2009 and 2016 (Moorman 2016). However, little research has specifically defined or measured social CRM capabilities to specify how they might influence business performance. Therefore, this study pursues several seemingly simple but critical questions: What are social CRM capabilities, and why are they important?

Trainor (2012, p. 321) defines social CRM as “the integration of traditional customer-facing activities with emergent social media applications to engage customers in collaborative conversations and enhance customer relationships.” Social CRM capabilities, as unique combinations of emerging technological resources and customer-centric management systems, extend traditional CRM capabilities by integrating the social functions and processes that emerge from firm–customer interactions, as well as customer–customer interactions (Greenberg 2010). Thus, to measure social CRM capabilities, we propose extending the conventional input–output stochastic frontier model, which represents a common tool to measure capabilities in a conventional sense (Battese and Coelli 1992; Dutta, Narasimhan, and Rajiv 1999, 2005; Xiong and Bharadwaj 2013). To specify the firm’s inputs and desired outcomes, we include social media resource inputs, in addition to traditional resource inputs, which derive from customers

who actively participate in beneficial relationships with firms (Malthouse et al. 2013). Rather than focusing solely on sales outcomes (Dutta, Narasimhan and Rajiv 1999; Xiong and Bharadwaj 2013), we also measure the firm's relationship with current and potential customers as a critical output of social CRM capabilities, with the realization that customer engagement is one of the most important benefits of social media. Accordingly, we test possible social CRM capabilities measures that feature both financial and customer relationship outcomes.

With these contributions, we extend extant literature by systematically defining and conceptualizing new social CRM capabilities that firms can build through social media. The proposed social CRM capability measure builds on an input–output stochastic frontier model. Furthermore, we test and verify our proposed measure with cross-industry panel data sets, which helps expand the generalizability of the findings about the relationship between firms' social CRM capabilities and performance. Accordingly, in the next section, we begin by conceptualizing and defining social CRM capabilities. We then review existing measures and apply our proposed measure of social CRM capabilities to firms in various sectors and industries, using actual corporate data about 232 companies gathered from the Facebook, COMPUSTAT North America, and Global Fundamentals annual databases over 2004–2014. After we detail our analyses and results, we conclude with some insights for theory and practice and potential areas for further research.

CONCEPTUALIZING/DEFINING SOCIAL CRM CAPABILITIES

CRM and Social Media

Market fragmentation and rapid change are ubiquitous; traditional communication channels are being supplemented by social media networking, as well as other novel marketing techniques (Day 2011). Rather than struggling to obtain feedback from customers, marketers

today must find ways to keep up with the floods of data coming to them from innumerable channels. Modern firms must track and understand what is being said about them, their products, and their competitors in user-generated content and social media channels, as well as establish and manage their own social media sites (Day 2011). Social media, which encompass a series of technological innovations (Web 2.0) in both hardware and software that facilitate inexpensive content creation, interaction, and interoperability by creative online users (Berthon et al. 2012), establish platforms for consumers to interact with and influence one another easily. They exert direct impacts on brand communities and produce high response rates and customer engagement, relative to traditional marketing methodologies (Trusov, Bucklin, and Pauwels 2009). Researchers also indicate that social media interactions or activities can influence both financial performance (Li and Stacks, 2015) and customer relationship (Buhalis and Mamalakis, 2015; Hudson, Huang, Roth, and Madden, 2016).

In a traditional CRM framework, an organization uses its knowledge of customers to manage customer relationships (Payne and Frow 2005; Verhoef et al. 2010). Reinartz, Krafft, and Hoyer (2004, p. 295) define this sort of CRM as a procedure that “entails the systematic and proactive management of relationships as they move from the beginning (initiation) to the end (termination), with execution across the various customer-facing contact channels.” Boulding et al. (2005, p. 157) also identify key elements: “CRM relates to strategy, the management of the dual creation of value, the intelligent use of data and technology, the acquisition of customer knowledge and the diffusion of this knowledge to the appropriate stakeholders, the development of appropriate (long-term) relationships with specific customers and/or customer groups, and the integration of processes across the many areas of the firm and across the network of firms that collaborate to generate customer value.” Thus CRM provides a strategic framework and method

for embedding information technology (IT) into marketing activities in support of the effort to create and maintain customer relationships (Trainor 2012). Rapp, Trainor, and Agnihotri (2010) propose in turn that CRM capability entails a combination and integration of various technology, human, and business resources. Their multidimensional CRM capability construct consists of static, operational, and strategic dimensions. Furthermore, research suggests that technology resources need to link with strategic resources, to achieve their interactive effects on customer relationships (Bharadwaj 2000; Chang, Park, and Chaïy 2010; Coltman 2007). An organization cannot improve its performance simply by investing more in IT; it needs to combine its CRM technology with customer-centric strategies to develop a new, valuable capability (Coltman 2007; Trainor 2012).

This traditional view of CRM technology highlights systems that provide support for various firm functions, such as sales (sales force automation), marketing (planning and budgeting, campaign and promotions management), data analysis (customer retention, customer lifetime value, customer satisfaction), and data integration (Jayachandran et al. 2005; Rapp, Trainor, and Agnihotri 2010; Trainor 2012). The rapidly growing popularity of social media in both consumer and business markets suggests a need to reconsider this traditional view though (Trainor 2012). Consumers participate actively in the co-creation of their experiences with firms, using social media to connect with other consumers and firms (Berthon et al. 2012; Hanna, Rohm, and Crittenden 2011; Reimann, Schilke, and Thomas 2010; Trainor et al. 2014). Changing customer behavior also encourages more customer–business interactions, achieved with the new capabilities developed through social media (Trainor 2012; Trainor et al. 2014). Social, creative consumers who generate value-added content in social media also fall outside traditional CRM frameworks (Berthon et al. 2012; Greenberg 2010). This expanded concept of

CRM reflects new capabilities enabled by the technological and social shifts brought about by social media networking (Trainor 2012; Trainor et al. 2014). Greenberg (2010) attempts to incorporate these technological and social changes, suggesting the terms “CRM 2.0” or “social CRM” to reflect the more collaborative, network-focused approach to managing customer relationships and describe new ways to develop and maintain customer relationships (Trainor 2012).

Social CRM Capabilities

Social CRM studies generally focus on the boundary between traditional and social CRM (Malthouse et al. 2013). Social CRM is an extension, not a replacement, of traditional CRM and comprises new capabilities associated with both firm–customer and customer–customer interactions (Greenberg 2010). A few studies that adopt a resource-based view (RBV) indicate that investments in IT can be integrated to form new capabilities that ultimately enhance firm performance (Malthouse et al. 2013; Mithas, Ramasubbu, and Sambamurthy 2011; Nath, Nachiappan, and Ramanathan 2010; Rapp, Trainor, and Agnihotri 2010). Previous studies also demonstrate that marketing capabilities (Morgan, Vorhies, and Mason 2009), e-marketing capabilities (Trainor et al. 2011), and CRM capabilities (Srinivasan and Moorman 2005) all can positively influence both customer relationships and organizational performance. Trainor et al. (2014) propose social CRM capabilities, as a unique combination of emerging technological resources and customer-centric management systems that lead to customer satisfaction, loyalty, and retention. As they demonstrate, social CRM capabilities are positively associated with customer relationship performance (Trainor et al. 2014).

Dutta, Narasimhan, and Rajiv’s capabilities definition as the efficiency. Dutta and colleagues (1999, 2005) define capabilities in general as the efficiency with which a firm uses

the inputs or resources available to it and converts them into whatever outcomes it pursues or its objectives. As this definition makes clear, capabilities represent an intermediate transformation step, between inputs (e.g., resources) and desired outcomes (e.g., objectives, such as sales). Their definition is consistent with the RBV. However, because it is difficult to observe capabilities directly, it requires inferences about how they convert resources into outcomes.

In addition, a marketing capability is not merely the possession of marketing-related resources; it requires the efficient integration and conversion of those resources into desired marketing outcomes. It depends on a firm's prior and consistent, ongoing investments (Bharadwaj, Varadarajan, and Fahy 1993; Dutta, Narasimhan, and Rajiv 1999, 2005). Recent studies also predict that investors consider firms' marketing capabilities when appraising firm value (e.g., Bahadir, Bharadwaj, and Srivastava 2008). Stock market investors gain insights into the firm's marketing capabilities by reviewing its historical marketing outcomes, relative to its marketing resources. For example, if two firms exhibit similar marketing and promotional efforts and comparable product technologies, the one that generates more sales revenue likely has greater marketing capability than the other. Social media also allow investors to observe the firm's efficiency in responding to market changes (e.g., how much and how quickly it learns from customers).

Network technology capability. Networking capability is a major benefit of Web 2.0. Consumers can control how information gets generated, created, organized, and shared (Bell and Loane 2010; Okazaki and Taylor 2013). As we noted previously, social media feature multiple technological innovations (Web 2.0) that have facilitated inexpensive content creation, interactions, and interoperability among users online (Berthon et al. 2012). Social networking sites also facilitate the effectiveness and spread of electronic word of mouth (eWOM), whether

to support information exchanges, provide recreational pleasure, or bring users together (Hennig-Thurau et al. 2004; Lee and Youn 2009). In turn, users rely on social media platforms to exchange brand- and product-related information (Chakravarty, Kumar, and Grewal 2014; Kumar 2013). Because users can interact with and influence each other, develop brand communities, and engage with firms on social media platforms (Pansari and Kumar 2017; Trusov, Bucklin, and Pauwels 2009), they can influence others' activities within their social network too. These social media influences create a ripple effect that extends beyond a customer's immediate social network, potentially creating chain reactions (Hogan, Lemon, and Libai 2003) that might ultimately determine the firm's profits (Kumar 2013; Lee and Grewal 2004).

Personal extensibility capability. Social media differ from traditional media in terms of the mobility they enable, due to their design and capacity (Parameswaran and Whinston 2007). Personal extensibility refers to a person's ability to overcome the friction of distance through communication (Okazaki and Taylor 2013). Researchers cite the impact of distance factors for international marketing (Malhotra, Sivakumar, and Zhu 2009). The concept of extensibility spans both distance (mobility) and time (immediacy) (Bluedorn, Kaufman, and Lane 1992; Harvey, Kiessling, and Richey 2008). Social media users can overcome both physical distance and time gaps by using personal electronic devices.

A Definition of social CRM capability. Combining these insights, we propose the following definition of social CRM capability: Social CRM capability refers to a firm's efficiency in integrating and converting social media marketing resources into desired sales revenue and customer relationship outcomes. With this definition, we extend Trainor and colleagues' (2014) definition and discussions of marketing capability. That is, Trainor's version

of social CRM capability focuses on customer interactions through social media technologies; we instead include it as a part of marketing capabilities, reflecting the firm's competency in obtaining, generating, organizing, and integrating information from customer engagement on social media, facilitated by the network technology and personal extensibility capabilities of social media, and then leveraging the customer information to maintain and improve its customer relationships, with efficient effects on its financial performance.

MEASURING SOCIAL CRM CAPABILITIES

Survey Approach

Trainor et al. (2014) took a survey approach to measure social CRM capabilities, using a scale from Srinivasan and Moorman (2005). Their measure of social CRM capabilities assumed an organization-wide system for acquiring, disseminating, and responding to customer information, such that three items assess information generation, four items refer to information dissemination, and six items assess responsiveness. Trainor et al. (2014) modified these scale items to refer to customer information generated from social media applications, then aggregated the items for each latent variable into single-scale scores to establish individual indicators of capabilities.

Input–Output Stochastic Frontier Model

A social CRM capability likely aims to achieve increased sales and improved customer satisfaction, through a better understanding of customer needs and distinctive targeting of appropriate customers. We propose measuring social CRM capability with an input–output stochastic frontier model that can predict the efficiencies of individual firms (Battese and Coelli 1992; Dutta, Narasimhan, and Rajiv 1999; Xiong and Bharadwaj 2013). This approach also

provides an appropriate econometric technique to model the firm's functional activities as an efficient frontier, relating productive resources to its functional objectives as long as the firm deploys those resources efficiently (Dutta, Narasimhan, and Rajiv 1999, 2005). The model includes two random components: the presence of inefficiency and a traditional random error (Battese and Coelli 1992). Previous studies use the inverse of a firm's functional inefficiency to measure its functional capability (Dutta, Narasimhan and Rajiv 1999, 2005; Narasimhan, Rajiv, and Dutta 2006; Xiong and Bharadwaj 2013). We specify the model items next and summarize them in Table 1.

Insert Table 1 about here

Social media resource inputs. In line with our definition, firms generate social CRM capabilities when they invest in technological resources to support social media and integrate those resources with customer-centric management systems. Organizations can adapt to rapidly changing market environments by introducing technical innovations, which lead to enhanced performance (Han, Kim, and Srivastava 1998). In this sense, organizations with high levels of social media usage are more likely to adapt to the social media environment and achieve an advantage by acquiring customer information and trust, before their competitors.

However, the interactivity inherent to social media has not been defined clearly but the two contrasting interpretations: “interpersonal view” and “machine interactivity” (Burton and Soboleva 2011). An interpersonal view (Macias and Lewis 2003) suggests that interactive communication occurs between individuals and organizations and ranges from non-interactive, one-way communications to quick reactions to messages to fully interactive communications in

which communication roles are totally interchangeable (Burton and Soboleva 2011; Rafaeli 1988). A machine interactivity view (Hoffman and Novak 1996) instead argues that interactivity is the extent to which users may modify messages they receive (Steuer 1992). Websites and social networking sites thus might offer different levels of interactivity, depending on whether they feature links, chat functions, or hyperlinks to external websites, for example (Burton and Soboleva 2011). Companies also can use social media sites to achieve interpersonal interactivity and support the exchange of messages between corporations and users by embedding hashtags/tags or replying to individual posts. Different types of social media posts created by companies also might vary in their level of machine interactivity, according to whether they use embedded hyperlinks in posts that users can click to access information or alternative media (e.g., video).

Therefore, in addition to traditional resource inputs, we add social media resource inputs to emphasize the various activities and interactions that take place between companies and individual consumers through social media. Because social CRM implies that customers engage actively with these companies, these inputs effectively represent social media resources (Malthouse et al. 2013).

Desired outcomes of social CRM capabilities. We start by identifying reasonable objectives of a firm. Focusing on CRM activities in social media, some objectives might include maximizing both financial and marketing performance; the inputs available for achieving these objectives include current and past social media usage. Social CRM capabilities emphasize the firm's ability to engage customers in collaborative conversations and enhance customer relationships, so we include relational outcomes such as customer satisfaction, loyalty, and retention in our research model. Hooley et al. (2005) and Rapp, Trainor, and Agnihotri (2010)

have shown that marketing capabilities lead to stronger customer relationships, which then improve customer satisfaction and loyalty. Technology-based literature also suggests that IT has empowered efficient, effective interactions between organizations and customers (Ahearne, Jelinek, and Rapp 2005; Coviello, Milley, and Marcolin 2001) and allows for coordinated captures and uses of customer information, which should lead to more effective responses (Jayachandran et al. 2005). Marketing technologies in particular positively influence customer satisfaction and relationship development through improved internal communications and information sharing (Wang and Kim 2017; Wu, Mahajan, and Balasubramanian 2003). For the resulting model, following Dutta and colleagues (1999), we use a Koyck lag function with higher weights for more recent years to derive measures of stock variables; resources from prior years can exert cumulative impacts on current outcomes (Dutta, Narasimhan, and Rajiv 1999). For example, we define SGASTOCK for period t as $SGASTOCK_t = \sum_{k=1}^{k=t} \gamma^{t-k} \times SGAExpense_k$, where γ represents the weight attached to the past value of selling, general, and administrative expenses. We apply a .5 weight (Dutta, Narasimhan, and Rajiv 2005) and also confirm that the results are robust to different weights. Other stock variable calculations feature similar methods.

We also control for industry and market conditions. We divide the firms by four-digit standard industrial classification (SIC) codes, and then for the estimation, we specify dummy variables reflecting each firm's four-digit SIC code. We use the stock variables as inputs in Equation 1. In addition, we derive the maximum likelihood estimate of the inefficiency term η_{it} , then rescale the estimate η_{it} to be between 0 and 100, and use $100 - \eta_{it}$ as the marketing capability measure (Xiong and Bharadwaj 2013). Thus,

$$\ln(Outcomes_{it}) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \ln(SGAS_{it}) + \alpha_2 \ln(RCS_{it}) + \alpha_3 \ln(SMR_{it}) + \alpha_4 MC_i + \varepsilon_{it} - \eta_{it}. \quad (1)$$

EMPIRICAL APPLICATION

We apply our proposed measure of social CRM capabilities to firms in different sectors and industries, using actual corporate data. To illustrate this estimation and explain how firms benefit from the capabilities, in the form of improved financial performance, we turn to an empirical model that establishes the direct relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance. We also consider potential moderating effects of social media usage on the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance, as we depict in Figure 1.

Insert Figure 1 about here

Social Media Data

We collected our primary social media data from Facebook. Some companies had multiple Facebook accounts, in which cases we selected those accounts that appear on each company's official website. To account for organizational policies regarding the use of social media, we included both the company's Facebook accounts and its main brands' Facebook accounts in our analysis. We also collected all different types of postings, such as plain text, photos, images, videos, or links from the Facebook accounts, starting with the day each company began using Facebook until December 31, 2014.

COMPUSTAT

We collected financial statement data from the COMPUSTAT North America and Global Fundamentals annual databases for a 34-year period (1980–2014). Then, we used the time span

of the firms' social media activities for the seven-year period from 2007 to 2014. We also collected control variables from COMPUSTAT, such as firm size, leverage, total sales, and industry categories.

ACSI

We collected customer satisfaction data from the American Customer Satisfaction Index (ACSI), which provides a customer-based measurement system to evaluate and enhance customer-related firm performance. It collects individual-level survey data for more than 300 major companies in more than 40 industries. The ACSI is designed to represent the economy as a whole, for which aggregated individual-level data produce customer satisfaction benchmarks at the company-, industry-, and national levels (Anderson, Fornell, and Lehmann 1994; Anderson, Fornell, and Mazvancheryl 2004; Fornell et al. 1996), such that an individual firm's index represents its served market's overall evaluation of total purchases and consumption experiences.

After we matched the ACSI list with COMPUSTAT data, we excluded companies that did not have Facebook accounts. The final sample thus includes 232 companies.

Measures

Social CRM capabilities. In line with our conceptualization of social CRM capability measures, we use information from corporate disclosures to inform our input–output stochastic frontier model (Battese and Coelli 1992; Dutta, Narasimhan, and Rajiv 1999, 2005; Xiong and Bharadwaj 2013) and predict the efficiencies of individual firms in an industry:

$$\ln(\text{Sales}_{it}) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \ln(\text{SGAS}_{it}) + \alpha_2 \ln(\text{RCS}_{it}) + \alpha_3 \ln(\text{SMR}_{it}) + \alpha_4 \text{MC}_i + \varepsilon_{it} - \eta_{it}. \quad (2)$$

Social CRM capabilities, which also reflect the firm's ability to engage customers in collaborative conversations and enhance customer relationships, require the inclusion of relational outcomes of customer satisfaction, loyalty, and retention in the research model.

Therefore, we measure social CRM capabilities, using both customer satisfaction and sales as outcomes:

$$\begin{aligned} (\ln(\text{Customer Satisfaction}_{it}) + \ln(\text{Sales}_{it}))/2 = & \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \ln(\text{SGAS}_{it}) + \alpha_2 \ln(\text{RCS}_{it}) + \alpha_3 \ln(\text{SMR}_{it}) \\ & + \alpha_4 \text{MC}_i + \varepsilon_{it} - \eta_{it}. \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

Social media usage. Social media technologies create environments that can engage customers in collaborative conversations and enhance customer relationships. Social media usage represents how much an organization uses social media technologies. Firms that actively use social media can increase awareness and emphasize their intentions to involve customers in interactive dialogue, which should increase the influence of their social CRM capabilities. Therefore, we include social media usage as a potential moderator. We measure social media usage with data collected from companies' Facebook accounts each year, namely, the number of posts by the company in each year.

Firm performance. We calculate Tobin's q by summing the market value of equity and the book value of debt, divided by the book value of the total assets for that period. All these financial data come from COMPUSTAT.

Control variables. We control for firm size, leverage, industry categories, total sales every year, and year fixed effects for firm and industry heterogeneity. We use the average total number of employees as an indicator variable for firm size and nine industry categories, with dummy variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics and Results of Panel Regressions

We used STATA 14.0 to generate descriptive statistics and conduct panel regressions. Table 2 contains the statistics of the inefficiency term η_{it} and the efficiency index $100 - \eta_{it}$

associated with sales outcome. Table 3 lists the results for both sales and customer satisfaction outcomes. As we noted, we derived the maximum likelihood estimate of the inefficiency term η_{it} and efficiency $100 - \eta_{it}$ for social CRM capabilities.

Insert Tables 2 and 3 about here

Table 4 presents the correlation matrix with the descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations, and correlations) for all variables. These results suggest that social CRM capabilities with sales outcomes relate positively to firm performance ($r = .5$) and customer satisfaction ($r = .06$). We also note similar correlations between social CRM capabilities and the combined sales and customer satisfaction outcomes for firm performance ($r = .11$) and customer satisfaction ($r = .01$). When we estimate the parameters using a fixed-effect panel regression (Table 5), we use Model 1 to represent the relationship of social CRM capability with sales outcomes and firm performance, as well as to test the moderating effect of social media usage that may strengthen or weaken the relationship between social CRM capability with sales outcomes and the firm performance. Model 2 reflects the relationship of social CRM capability with both customer satisfaction and sales outcomes and firm performance, again adding social media as a potential moderator. In both models, social CRM capabilities have positive, statistically significant effects ($p < .01$) on firm performance. The coefficient of social CRM capabilities when we consider both customer satisfaction and sales outcomes is larger than that for only sales outcomes. The R-square values are similar across the two models; overall, all the results are similar. Thus, social CRM capabilities appear critical when companies merge social media into their marketing strategies to improve firm performance.

In addition, the statistically significant, positive coefficient of social media usage \times social CRM capabilities with sales outcomes ($p < .1$) confirms that social media usage positively moderates the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance. However, we do not find statistical evidence of moderating effects by social media usage on the relationship between social CRM capabilities with the combination of customer satisfaction and sales outcomes and firm performance.

Insert Tables 4 and 5 about here

CONTRIBUTIONS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

This study conceptualizes and defines the new construct of social CRM capabilities, which represent a new form of CRM capabilities that leverage social media. It also validates the role of social CRM capabilities in determining business performance. We examine and test the effects of social CRM capabilities on firms' financial performance, as well as contingent effects of social media usage, thus confirming that social CRM capabilities offer a strong predictor of firm performance. Firms should not treat social media investments as net costs; rather, social media provide significant resources for building a new form of CRM capabilities that can support organizational transformation and enhance firm value.

In turn, our research contributes to prior literature in three main respects. First, we systematically define and conceptualize new social CRM capabilities. Previous literature included social CRM capability among marketing capabilities and focused on customer interactions through social media technologies; our definition instead details the firm's

competency in obtaining, generating, organizing, and integrating information from customer engagement, facilitated by network technology and personal extensibility capabilities of social media; using customer information to maintain and improve customer relationships; and efficiently influencing the firm's financial performance.

Second, we offer an alternative to survey approaches to measuring social CRM capabilities. Our more quantitative method relies on the input–output stochastic frontier model (Battese and Coelli 1992; Dutta, Narasimhan, and Rajiv 1999; Xiong and Bharadwaj 2013). In addition, we propose a social CRM capability measure in accordance with this input–output stochastic frontier model that reflects its capacity to enhance both the perceived value of the firm's products and the firm's relationships with current and potential customers. These goal can be manifested as sales growth and improved customer satisfaction, with better allocations and uses of both traditional marketing resources and social media resources. The input–output conceptualization of firm capabilities makes the stochastic frontier estimation methodology well suited to our definition and study.

Third, we verify the proposed measure and expand the generalizability of the relationship between firms' social CRM capabilities and performance by using cross-industry panel data sets. With Tobin's q as the outcome variable, this study validates the role of social CRM capabilities as leading determinants of business performance.

However, our approach to measuring social CRM capabilities also entails some limitations, which suggest directions for further research. First, the social media resource inputs in our data set refer to only one social media website (Facebook), so the results cannot be generalized to all social media. Continued research should include other leading social media sites, which may produce a more accurate, comprehensive measure. Researchers also may

identify differences across social media (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, YouTube) when it comes to measuring social CRM capabilities. Such analyses could shed light on the different social CRM capabilities that accrue when companies operate multiple accounts on various sites. Second, because we sought comparable data, the firms that we examined are large, publicly traded corporations, and the findings may not be representative of private corporations or small firms. If data permit, it would be fruitful to examine our social CRM capabilities measure among smaller or private companies. Third, this study should be extended to different countries. Social media use may tend to be greater, with more active information exchanges, in collectivist cultures, in which people pursue greater connectedness (Okazaki and Taylor 2013). A potential next step might be to incorporate our proposed social CRM capabilities measure into the theoretical or empirical models that underlie international social media marketing strategy studies. Cross-country research may produce stronger validations and evidence of the generalizability of our proposed measure.

REFERENCE

- Ahearne, Michael, Ronald Jelinek, and Adam Rapp (2005), "Moving Beyond the Direct Effect of Sfa Adoption on Salesperson Performance: Training and Support as Key Moderating Factors." *Industrial Marketing Management* 34.4, 379-88.
- Anderson, Eugene W, Claes Fornell, and Donald R Lehmann (1994), "Customer Satisfaction, Market Share, and Profitability: Findings from Sweden." *Journal of Marketing*, 53-66.
- Anderson, Eugene W, Claes Fornell, and Sanal K Mazvancheryl (2004), "Customer Satisfaction and Shareholder Value." *Journal of Marketing* 68.4, 172-85.
- Bahadir, S Cem, Sundar G Bharadwaj, and Rajendra K Srivastava (2008), "Financial Value of Brands in Mergers and Acquisitions: Is Value in the Eye of the Beholder?" *Journal of Marketing* 72.6, 49-64.
- Battese, George E and Tim J Coelli (1992), "Frontier Production Functions, Technical Efficiency and Panel Data: With Application to Paddy Farmers in India." *Journal of Productivity Analysis* 3, 153-69.
- Bell, Jim and Sharon Loane (2010), "'New-Wave' Global Firms: Web 2.0 and Sme Internationalisation." *Journal of Marketing Management* 26.3-4, 213-29.
- Berthon, Pierre R, Leyland F Pitt, Kirk Plangger, and Daniel Shapiro (2012), "Marketing Meets Web 2.0, Social Media, and Creative Consumers: Implications for International Marketing Strategy." *Business Horizons* 55.3, 261-71.
- Bharadwaj, Anandhi S (2000), "A Resource-Based Perspective on Information Technology Capability and Firm Performance: An Empirical Investigation." *MIS Quarterly* 24.1, 169-96.
- Bharadwaj, Sundar G, P Rajan Varadarajan, and John Fahy (1993), "Sustainable Competitive Advantage in Service Industries: A Conceptual Model and Research Propositions." *The Journal of Marketing*, 83-99.
- Bluedorn, Allen C, Carol Felker Kaufman, and Paul M Lane (1992), "How Many Things Do You Like to Do at Once? An Introduction to Monochronic and Polychronic Time." *The Executive* 6.4, 17-26.

- Boulding, William, Richard Staelin, Michael Ehret, and Wesley J Johnston (2005), "A Customer Relationship Management Roadmap: What Is Known, Potential Pitfalls, and Where to Go." *Journal of Marketing* 69.4, 155-66.
- Buhalis, Dimitrios and Emmanouil Mamalakis (2015), "Social media return on investment and performance evaluation in the hotel industry context." In *Information and Communication Technologies in Tourism*, 241-253.
- Burton, Suzan and Alena Soboleva (2011), "Interactive or Reactive? Marketing with Twitter." *Journal of Consumer Marketing* 28.7, 491-99.
- Chakravarty, Anindita, Alok Kumar, and Rajdeep Grewal (2014), "Customer Orientation Structure for Internet-Based Business-to-Business Platform Firms." *Journal of Marketing* 78.5, 1-23.
- Chang, Woojung, Jeong Eun Park, and Seoil Cha (2010), "How Does CRM Technology Transform into Organizational Performance? A Mediating Role of Marketing Capability." *Journal of Business Research* 63.8, 849-55.
- Coltman, Tim (2007), "Can Superior CRM Capabilities Improve Performance in Banking." *Journal of Financial Services Marketing* 12.2, 102-14.
- Coviello, Nicole, Roger Milley, and Barbara Marcolin (2001), "Understanding IT-Enabled Interactivity in Contemporary Marketing." *Journal of Interactive Marketing* 15.4, 18-33.
- Day, George S (2011), "Closing the Marketing Capabilities Gap." *Journal of Marketing* 75.4, 183-95.
- Dutta, Shantanu, OM Narasimhan, and Surendra Rajiv (1999), "Success in High-Technology Markets: Is Marketing Capability Critical?" *Marketing Science* 18.4, 547-68.
- Dutta, Shantanu, OM Narasimhan, and Surendra Rajiv (2005), "Research Notes and Commentaries Conceptualizing and Measuring Capabilities: Methodology and Empirical Application." *Strategic Management Journal* 26.3, 277-85.
- Fornell, Claes, Michael D Johnson, Eugene W Anderson, Jaesung Cha, and Barbara Everitt Bryant (1996), "The American Customer Satisfaction Index: Nature, Purpose, and Findings." *Journal of Marketing* 60.4, 7-18.
- Greenberg, Paul (2010), "The Impact of Crm 2.0 on Customer Insight." *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing* 25.6, 410-19.

- Han, Jin K, Namwoon Kim, and Rajendra K Srivastava (1998), "Market Orientation and Organizational Performance: Is Innovation a Missing Link?" *Journal of Marketing* 62, 30-45.
- Hanna, Richard, Andrew Rohm, and Victoria L Crittenden (2011), "We're All Connected: The Power of the Social Media Ecosystem." *Business Horizons* 54.3, 265-73.
- Harvey, Michael G, Timothy S Kiessling, and R Glenn Richey (2008), "Global Social Time Perspectives in Marketing: A Strategic Reference Point Theory Application." *International Marketing Review* 25.2, 146-65.
- Hennig-Thurau, Thorsten, Kevin P Gwinner, Gianfranco Walsh, and Dwayne D Gremler (2004), "Electronic Word of Mouth Via Consumer-Opinion Platforms: What Motivates Consumers to Articulate Themselves on the Internet?" *Journal of Interactive Marketing* 18.1, 38-52.
- Hoffman, Donna L and Thomas P Novak (1996), "Marketing in Hypermedia Computer-Mediated Environments: Conceptual Foundations." *Journal of Marketing* 60.3, 50-68.
- Hogan, John E, Katherine N Lemon, and Barak Libai (2003), "What Is the True Value of a Lost Customer?" *Journal of Service Research* 5.3, 196-208.
- Hooley, Graham J, Gordon E Greenley, John W Cadogan, and John Fahy (2005), "The Performance Impact of Marketing Resources." *Journal of Business Research* 58.1, 18-27.
- Hudson, Simon, Li Huang, Martin S. Roth, and Thomas J. Madden (2016), "The influence of social media interactions on consumer-brand relationships: A three-country study of brand perceptions and marketing behaviors." *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 33.1, 27-41.
- Jayachandran, Satish, Subhash Sharma, Peter Kaufman, and Pushkala Raman (2005), "The Role of Relational Information Processes and Technology Use in Customer Relationship Management." *Journal of Marketing* 69.4, 177-92.
- Kumar, V (2013), *Profitable Customer Engagement: Concept, Metrics and Strategies*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Lee, Mira and Seounmi Youn (2009), "Electronic Word of Mouth (Ewom) How Ewom Platforms Influence Consumer Product Judgement." *International Journal of Advertising* 28.3, 473-99.

- Lee, Ruby P and Rajdeep Grewal (2004), "Strategic Responses to New Technologies and Their Impact on Firm Performance." *Journal of Marketing* 68.4, 157-71.
- Li, Cong and Don W. Stacks (2015). "Measuring the impact of social media on business profit and success: A Fortune 500 perspective." New York, NY:Peter Lang.
- Macias, Wendy and Liza Stavchansky Lewis (2003), "A Content Analysis of Direct-to-Consumer (Dtc) Prescription Drug Web Sites." *Journal of Advertising* 32.4, 43-56.
- Malhotra, Shavin, K Sivakumar, and PengCheng Zhu (2009), "Distance Factors and Target Market Selection: The Moderating Effect of Market Potential." *International Marketing Review* 26.6, 651-73.
- Malthouse, Edward C, Michael Haenlein, Bernd Skiera, Egbert Wege, and Michael Zhang (2013), "Managing Customer Relationships in the Social Media Era: Introducing the Social CRM House." *Journal of Interactive Marketing* 27.4, 270-80.
- Mithas, Sunil, Narayan Ramasubbu, and Vailabh Sambamurthy (2011), "How Information Management Capability Influences Firm Performance." *MIS Quarterly* 35.1, 237-56.
- Moorman, Christine (2016), "CMO Survey Report: Highlights and Insights." in *The CMO Survey*. (accessed October 30, 2017) [available at https://cmosurvey.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/15/2018/01/The_CMO_Survey-Highlights_and_Insights-Aug-2016.pdf]
- Morgan, Neil A, Douglas W Vorhies, and Charlotte H Mason (2009), "Market Orientation, Marketing Capabilities, and Firm Performance." *Strategic Management Journal* 30.8, 909-20.
- Narasimhan, Om, Surendra Rajiv, and Shantanu Dutta (2006), "Absorptive Capacity in High-Technology Markets: The Competitive Advantage of the Haves." *Marketing Science* 25.5, 510-24.
- Nath, Prithwiraj, Subramanian Nachiappan, and Ramakrishnan Ramanathan (2010), "The Impact of Marketing Capability, Operations Capability and Diversification Strategy on Performance: A Resource-Based View." *Industrial Marketing Management* 39.2, 317-29.
- Okazaki, Shintaro and Charles R Taylor (2013), "Social Media and International Advertising: Theoretical Challenges and Future Directions." *International Marketing Review* 30.1, 56-71.

- Pansari, Anita and V. Kumar (2017), "Customer Engagement: The Construct, Antecedents, and Consequences." *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science* 45.3, 294-311.
- Parameswaran, Manoj and Andrew B Whinston (2007), "Social Computing: An Overview." *Communications of the Association for Information Systems* 19.1, 762-80.
- Payne, Adrian and Pennie Frow (2005), "A Strategic Framework for Customer Relationship Management." *Journal of Marketing* 69.4, 167-76.
- Rafaeli, Sheizaf (1988), "Interactivity: From New Media to Communication." in *Advancing Communication Science: Mergine Mass and Interpersonal Processess*, Newbery Park, CA: Sage Publications, 110-34.
- Rapp, Adam, Lauren Skinner Beitelspacher, Dhruv Grewal, and Douglas E Hughes (2013), "Understanding Social Media Effects across Seller, Retailer, and Consumer Interactions." *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science* 41.5, 547-66.
- Rapp, Adam, Kevin J Trainor, and Raj Agnihotri (2010), "Performance Implications of Customer-Linking Capabilities: Examining the Complementary Role of Customer Orientation and Crm Technology." *Journal of Business Research* 63.11, 1229-36.
- Reimann, Martin, Oliver Schilke, and Jacquelyn S Thomas (2010), "Customer Relationship Management and Firm Performance: The Mediating Role of Business Strategy." *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science* 38.3, 326-46.
- Reinartz, Werner, Manfred Krafft, and Wayne D Hoyer (2004), "The Customer Relationship Management Process: Its Measurement and Impact on Performance." *Journal of Marketing Research* 41.3, 293-305.
- Srinivasan, Raji and Christine Moorman (2005), "Strategic Firm Commitments and Rewards for Customer Relationship Management in Online Retailing." *Journal of Marketing* 69.4, 193-200.
- Steuer, Jonathan (1992), "Defining Virtual Reality: Dimensions Determining Telepresence." *Journal of Communication* 42.4, 73-93.
- Trainor, Kevin J (2012), "Relating Social Media Technologies to Performance: A Capabilities-Based Perspective." *Journal of Personal Selling and Sales Management*.3, 317-31.
- Trainor, Kevin J, James Mick Andzulis, Adam Rapp, and Raj Agnihotri (2014), "Social Media Technology Usage and Customer Relationship Performance: A Capabilities-Based Examination of Social Crm." *Journal of Business Research* 67.6, 1201-08.

- Trainor, Kevin J, Adam Rapp, Lauren Skinner Beitelspacher, and Niels Schillewaert (2011), "Integrating Information Technology and Marketing: An Examination of the Drivers and Outcomes of E-Marketing Capability." *Industrial Marketing Management* 40.1, 162-74.
- Trusov, Michael, Randolph E Bucklin, and Koen Pauwels (2009), "Effects of Word-of-Mouth Versus Traditional Marketing: Findings from an Internet Social Networking Site." *Journal of Marketing* 73.5, 90-102.
- Verhoef, Peter C, Rajkumar Venkatesan, Leigh McAlister, Edward C Malthouse, Manfred Krafft, and Shankar Ganesan (2010), "CRM in Data-Rich Multichannel Retailing Environments: A Review and Future Research Directions." *Journal of Interactive Marketing* 24.2, 121-37.
- Wang, Zhan and Hyun Gon Kim (2017), "Can Social Media Marketing Improve Customer Relationship Capabilities and Firm Performance? Dynamic Capability Perspective." *Journal of Interactive Marketing* 39, 15-26.
- Wu, Fang, Vijay Mahajan, and Sridhar Balasubramanian (2003), "An Analysis of E-Business Adoption and Its Impact on Business Performance." *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science* 31.4, 425-47.
- Xiong, Guiyang and Sundar Bharadwaj (2013), "Asymmetric Roles of Advertising and Marketing Capability in Financial Returns to News: Turning Bad into Good and Good into Great." *Journal of Marketing Research* 50.6, 706-24.

Figure 1. Empirical Model

Table 1. Items used in the stochastic frontier model of social CRM capabilities

	Item	Description
1	Social media resource inputs (SMR): HasTag, HasLink, HasVideo, IsReply, HasImage	HasTag: Number of posts that contain tags HasLink: Number of posts that contain superlinks HasVideo: Number of posts that contain videos IsReply: Number of posts that are replies to others HasImage: Number of posts that contain images
2	Sales, general, and administrative stock (SGAS)	Sales, general, and administrative expense
3	Receivable stock (RCS)	Accounts receivable
4	Industry and market conditions (MC)	Dummy variables based on the four-digit SIC code of firm <i>i</i>
5	Sales outcome	Total sales
6	Customer satisfaction outcome	ACSI indexes

Table 2. Inefficiency and efficiency index, sales outcomes

Term	Sample Size	Mean	S.D.	Min	Max
Inefficiency index (η_{it})	232	11.96	1.90	7.39	16.19
Efficiency index ($100-\eta_{it}$)	232	88.04	1.90	83.80	92.60

Table 3. Inefficiency and efficiency index, customer satisfaction and sales outcomes

Term	Sample Size	Mean	S.D.	Min	Max
Inefficiency index (η_{it})	232	7.47	0.69	5.57	8.94
Efficiency index ($100-\eta_{it}$)	232	92.53	0.69	91.05	94.42

Table 4. Correlation matrix and descriptive statistics

No.	Variable	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	Firm performance (Tobin's q)	4.11	8.06	1.00								
2	Year	2009	3.16	0.06	1.00							
3	Social CRM capabilities*	88.04	1.90	0.05	0.01	1.00						
4	Social CRM capabilities**	92.52	0.69	0.11	0.02	0.92	1.00					
5	Social media usage	11.37	17.87	0.01	0.38	-0.17	-0.11	1.00				
6	Sales	9.30	2.47	-0.10	-0.02	-0.92	-0.98	0.11	1.00			
7	Employee	3.64	1.84	-0.18	-0.03	-0.65	-0.77	0.03	0.80	1.00		
8	Leverage	0.22	1.37	-0.15	-0.01	-0.25	-0.27	-0.02	0.27	0.15	1.00	
9	Customer satisfaction	76.55	5.71	-0.11	0.07	0.06	0.01	0.05	-0.04	0.01	0.27	1.00

* Sales outcomes.

** Customer satisfaction and sales outcomes.

Table 5. Results of fixed-effect (within) panel regressions

Models	1		2	
Dependent variable	Tobin's q	Tobin's q	Tobin's q	Tobin's q
Constant	-429.921 (131.726)**	-526.561 (137.439)***	-1,135.774 (374.327)**	-1,148.376 (378.724)**
Social CRM capability	4.085 (1.380)**	5.044 (1.432)**	11.69 (3.940)**	11.82 (3.987)**
Social media usage		-0.226 (0.023)		-0.007 (0.016)
Social media usage × Social CRM capability		0.812 (0.367)*		0.108 (0.404)
Sales	8.244 (2.023)***	8.800 (2.024)***	5.376 (1.771)**	5.558 (1.767)**
Employee	-2.954 (1.216)*	-2.798 (1.210)*	-0.877 (1.011)	-0.786 (1.009)
Leverage	-8.948 (7.142)	-6.653 (7.174)	-12.144 (5.997)*	-12.706 (5.987)*
Customer satisfaction	0.075 (0.072)	0.751 (0.723)	0.128 (0.062)*	0.135 (0.062)*
Industry fixed	Included	Included	Included	Included
Year fixed	Included	Included	Included	Included
R-square	0.12	0.14	0.10	0.10

* $p < .10$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$.